

A Radiation-Tolerant All-Digital Phase-Locked Loop with Fast Recovery from Single-Event Effects

Qichao Ma, Stefan Biereigel, Paul Leroux, Jeffrey Prinzie

Abstract—This paper presents a radiation-tolerant all-digital phase-locked loop (ADPLL) with fast recovery from Single-Event Effects (SEEs) occurring in the inductor of the LC oscillator. The proposed ADPLL can detect the phase error due to SEEs and track the frequency error by switching the bandwidth of the loop. Heavy ion tests confirm that our proposed fast recovery technique significantly decreases the recovery time under different LET. Laser tests were conducted to further study the recovery process. When exposed to 3 nJ laser pulses at 1064 nm, the recovery time is reduced from 37 μ s to 6 μ s. In steady state, the ADPLL operates at 2.56 GHz with a power consumption of 14.6 mW and an integral jitter of 0.3 ps from 12 kHz to 20 MHz.

Index Terms—all-digital phase locked loop (ADPLL), radiation hardened by design, bandwidth switching, single-event effect (SEE)

I. INTRODUCTION

PHASE-Locked Loops (PLLs) play an important role in many high-speed applications, such as clock generation and frequency synthesis. In radiation environments, PLLs have been shown to be vulnerable to SEEs [1]–[4]. For the digital building blocks, redundancy techniques like the Dual Interlocked Storage Cell (DICE) and Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) are commonly used to provide reliable immunity against SEEs [5], [6]. However, the Charge Pump (CP) and Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO) still remain sensitive to SEEs [7], [8]. Ion strikes in the charge pump can cause errors at the VCO tuning node, resulting in frequency perturbations at the PLL output. In the literature, many efforts can be found to harden the charge pump such as the voltage-based charge pump [9] and the source switched charge pump [10]. The VCO can be implemented as either an LC-tank oscillator or a ring oscillator. Ring oscillators are more prone to frequency drift due to Total Ionizing Dose (TID) effects, whereas the LC-tank oscillators are more susceptible to SEEs because of the sensitive varactors [11]. Recently, SEEs stimulated by heavy ion irradiation are also observed in the planar spiral inductors of these oscillators, leading to transient frequency errors lasting several milliseconds [12], [13].

Compared to traditional PLLs, ADPLLs replace most of the sensitive analog building blocks with digital blocks [14]. A Bang-Bang Phase Detector (BBPD), combined with a digital loop filter is employed instead of a Phase-Frequency Detector (PFD) and CP to compare the phase difference between the feedback clock and the reference clock, thereby tuning the

oscillator. Single Event Up sets (SEUs) in the highly nonlinear BBPD will only affect the PLL for one reference clock cycle, and the resulting frequency error is generally too small to be distinguished from noise. To achieve a better noise performance, an LC Digital Controlled Oscillator (LC DCO) is preferable at cost of the area, as the ring oscillator is normally considered to be very susceptible to the supply noise [15] and has a large phase noise. A varactor-less LC DCO can use custom switched-capacitor cells providing better radiation immunity than varactor based DCOs [16]. However, despite these improvements, SEEs in the inductor of LC DCOs still persist, leading to prominent phase errors. Due to the high non-linearity of the BBPD, the loop requires an extended duration to effectively track these errors.

Bandwidth Switching, also known as gear shifting, is frequently used during frequency acquisition of a PLL [17]. When switching to a new channel frequency, a wide loop bandwidth is initially adopted to speed up the locking process, which is then seamlessly scaled down for better noise performance [18]. However, unlike an instantaneous frequency error, the SEE induced in the inductor due to high-energy particles will cause a frequency error with an extended decay period [12], [13]. This frequency deviation subsequently translates into a phase error due to the integrative nature of the DCO.

In this paper, we propose a radiation-tolerant ADPLL capable of rapidly recovering from SEE perturbations in the inductor of a DCO in a commercial 65 nm technology. The proposed ADPLL rapidly detects an SEE in the PLL and promptly recovers by adjusting the loop bandwidth.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the architecture of the ADPLL. Section III outlines the modeling and implementation of the proposed fast recovery mechanism. Heavy ion tests and laser tests are presented in Section IV and Section V, respectively. Conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. ADPLL ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the proposed ADPLL is illustrated in Fig. 1. The BBPD compares the phase difference between the reference clock and the scaled DCO clock, outputting +1 and -1 for a leading and lagging DCO phase, respectively. Without fast recovery, the Digital Loop Filter (DLF) functions as a low-pass filter with proportional and integral path. An additional Sigma-Delta Modulator (SDM) is incorporated to improve the frequency tuning resolution. Except for the varactorless DCO (previously published in [16], demonstrating high levels of TID tolerance) and the BBPD, all building blocks are hardened

Q. Ma, P. Leroux, J. Prinzie are with KU Leuven, 3000 Leuven, Belgium (e-mail: qichao.ma@kuleuven.be)

S. Biereigel is with CERN, 1211 Geneva, Switzerland (email: stefan.biereigel@cern.ch)

Fig. 1. ADPLL Architecture

using TMR [19]. As discussed later in section. III, SEUs in the BBPD will not affect the PLL such that TMR can be omitted.

The concept of bandwidth switching is illustrated in Fig. 2 (a). During frequency acquisition, fast loop dynamics are desirable to reduce the settling time initially, whereas phase noise is not important at that time [20]. When the PLL is locked, a reduced bandwidth is desired in order to suppress the shaped high frequency noise [21]. The bandwidth can be switched several times to guarantee the whole process is hitless. By switching the bandwidth in this manner, the PLL can achieve fast locking and maintain low output jitter after locking.

The proposed SEE mitigation mechanism operates as follows: the BBPD output is averaged in a moving average filter to detect if the ADPLL is locked. When ADPLL is locked, the mean BBPD output value is zero and the fast recovery mechanism is inactive.

However, if a perturbation occurs, such as a SEE in the inductor, leading to a frequency error that accumulates to phase error, the averaged BBPD output will abruptly deviate from zero. Consequently, the loop bandwidth is temporarily increased to expedite the recovery process. After the loop can fully track the frequency error, the loop bandwidth is gradually switched back to its original value.

III. MODELING AND IMPLEMENTATION

As explained in the previous section, to enhance the recovery speed from an SEE in the inductor, it is essential to detect the locking state of the loop and establish a suitable bandwidth to track the frequency error until its impact diminishes. In this paper, the recovery time is defined as the first time the ADPLL output frequency error exceeds the maximum noise level until the last time when frequency error no longer exceeds the frequency error. It includes both the detection time and the bandwidth switching time as shown in Fig.2

A. Detection of the SEEs

Detection of SEEs in the ADPLL loop is achieved by calculating the average of the BBPD output over a short period and comparing its value with a threshold. When the ADPLL is locked, the BBPD output produces a sequence of random output decisions of +1 and -1 (For clarity, we scaled the BBPD output in Fig. 2 (b)), with a short-term mean value of

Fig. 2. (a) Locking process with bandwidth switching. (b) Averaged BBPD output

zero. In practice, as shown in Fig. 2 (b), the averaged BBPD output may fluctuate even in the locked state due to phase noise and the nonlinear nature of the BBPD. The fluctuation level depends on the phase noise of the ADPLL output and the number of samples N used to calculate the average. A larger value of N results in a lower fluctuation level but comes at the cost of increased delay while calculating the average. In addition, it results in higher power consumption and larger silicon area. Since the averaged BBPD output varies around zero, a threshold value is set based on the noise to avoid accidental triggering of the fast recovery mechanism. When a frequency error occurs due to an SEE, the frequency error accumulates into a phase error and is detected by the BBPD. In such case, the loop bandwidth is insufficient to track this sudden frequency error in one cycle, and the BBPD will generate a burst of output bits of the same sign to track the phase error [22]. As a result, the averaged BBPD output will start to increase or decrease (depending on the sign of BBPD output) from somewhere below the threshold and exceeds the threshold in the end, thus triggering the bandwidth switching.

The detection speed is essential to the whole recovery speed and the ADPLL peak output frequency error. After an SEE occurs, if the bandwidth can be triggered earlier, the loop can track the frequency perturbation more quickly, leading to a lower peak frequency error and phase error. There are two main factors that impact the detection speed. Firstly, the threshold to trigger the bandwidth switching must be carefully chosen to avoid significantly increasing the detection time, as the bandwidth switching is triggered after the averaged BBPD output exceeds the threshold. For a larger threshold, the circuit will have to wait longer before the bandwidth switching is activated. As a result, more frequency error will accumulate in the loop, prolonging the recovery time.

In addition to the threshold, the BBPD compares the DCO feedback clock with the reference clock. Increasing the reference clock will enhance the detection speed at the cost of higher power consumption. A higher reference clock frequency causes the BBPD output to accumulate more quickly after the SEE, thus triggering the bandwidth switching earlier, leading to a reduction on both the peak frequency error and recovery time.

B. Bandwidth switching

Once the averaged BBPD output exceeds the threshold, the bandwidth switching process will be engaged to increase the bandwidth and rapidly track the frequency error.

To optimize phase noise performance, the bandwidth of the ADPLL is typically selected as a balance between reference phase noise and DCO phase noise. When switching the loop bandwidth from a higher level to its original level, the total output phase noise decreases. Thus, for each downshift of the loop bandwidth, the phase error of the ADPLL output decreases accordingly.

When the bandwidth switching is triggered, to ensure the whole locking process is hitless and does not introduce additional frequency/phase errors, the bandwidth can be gradually switched in several steps, starting from the highest bandwidth to the lowest bandwidth. For each bandwidth level, the $\frac{\beta}{\alpha}$ ratio is kept constant and the bandwidth is boosted by increasing both β and α by a factor of 2 for easy implementation in hardware [17]. The highest bandwidth level needs to be maintained for enough time until the loop is able to fully track the frequency error, as shown in Fig. 2 (a). After that, the gain is switched to next level and this process is repeated several times until it reaches its original value for optimal phase noise performance. The switching time for each level is determined by when the frequency error at each level falls within its corresponding noise range. Due to the exponential decay of the frequency error induced by SEEs in the inductor, the PLL should effectively track the time-varying frequency transient. The initial bandwidth switching time should be chosen long enough to successfully track the initial frequency jump. When down-shifting the bandwidth, even though the PLL corrected the frequency error, the frequency is still varying with time as the SEE decays. Therefore, it is essential to ensure the integral gain of the PLL is sufficiently large to track the frequency decay smoothly.

As explained earlier, adopting a higher bandwidth improves the locking time. However, an excessively large bandwidth requires many switching steps, which may degrade recovery time and increase both power consumption and silicon area. To determine the trade-off between bandwidth level and recovery time, a behavioral model based on Fig. 3 was developed in MATLAB. As illustrated in Fig.3, noise sources are also included in this model, where σ_{REF} refers to the reference phase noise, σ_{QB} refers to the BBPD quantization noise and σ_{DCO} refers to the DCO phase noise. For simplicity, the MASH 1-1 sigma-delta modulator is not shown in this figure [23]. The SEEs are modeled by an exponential waveform with peak value and decay time equal to our previous collected data from heavy ion tests [12], [13].

Fig. 3. Discrete-time model of the ADPLL

Our study shows that three bandwidth levels were a good compromise to achieve the fastest recovery time without introducing too much silicon area.

C. Implementation

The proposed circuit was manufactured in a commercial 65 nm CMOS process with a nominal supply voltage of 1.2 V. The DCO in this ADPLL, shown in Fig. 4, was reused from our previous work [16]. The DCO was designed operating at 2.56 GHz with a tuning range of around 20% to cover the process variation and the TID related variations. Both the PVT and the acquisition bank cells are implemented using the bottom-pinning switch architecture [24]. The DCO is fanout to three identical output buffers, which allows for hardening the remainder of the circuit against SEE by full TMR technique. A prescaler which is also triplicated was added at the output of the buffers, resulting in a 1.28 GHz output frequency.

The BBPD used in this design is implemented using simple flip-flops from the standard library. An SEE occurring in the BBPD will affect only one cycle of the input of the digital filter and will be masked by noise and the non-linear behavior of the BBPD. Since a margin is maintained between the fluctuation level and the threshold, a single-cycle BBPD output flip caused by an SEE will not impact the ADPLL output or trigger the fast recovery mechanism.

The rest of building blocks of ADPLL were designed in standard digital design flow with standard digital cells provided by foundry. All digital blocks are clocked using frequencies generated by the Feedback Divider (FBDIV), which provides divided frequencies at 40 MHz, 80 MHz, 160 MHz, 320 MHz, 640 MHz. Since the DCO output is triplicated, the divider can also be protected from SEEs by TMR. Full triplicating of the clock signals is necessary to mitigate the simultaneous corruption of redundant memory elements by SET affecting their common clock tree, which has catastrophic consequences when affecting the digital loop filter registers. The SDM is clocked at 640 MHz and the rest of digital blocks can operate at 40 MHz, 80 MHz, 160 MHz or 320 MHz. To improve the SEEs tolerance, each replica of the TMR cell is placed at least 20 μm away from the other replica. The digital cells were triplicated by using the TMRG tools [19].

Fig. 6 shows the micrograph of the ADPLL which takes an area of 2 mm².

IV. BOARDBEAM HEAVY ION TEST

To validate our proposed fast recovery technique. Broad-beam heavy ion tests were conducted at the Radiation Effects facility in the Department of Physics at the University of Jyväskylä. The ADPLL configured in three different

Fig. 4. DCO schematic

Fig. 5. Digitally switched capacitor cells with bottom-pinning biasing [24]

modes was exposed to three different ions (Xe, Kr, and Ar) with Linear Energy Transfer (LET) values ranging from $58.5 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$ to $9.7 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$. For each ion, a fluence of $1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ ions}/\text{cm}^2$ and a flux of $5000 \text{ ions}/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ was achieved for each ADPLL configuration. Due to limitations in beam time, only the open-loop data for Kr was obtained with a fluence of $0.6 \times 10^6 \text{ ions}/\text{cm}^2$. The tests were conducted in air mode without tilting.

During the test, A 40 MHz clock provided from a SKYWORKS SI570-PROG-EVB board was employed as the reference clock. Different configurations including loop gain, switching time for each bandwidth level and the threshold to trigger the fast recovery can be set through SPI. The ADPLL

Fig. 6. Micrograph of the die

Fig. 7. Peak frequency error measurement

operated at 2.56 GHz with a prescaler of 2 at the output of DCO, yielding a output frequency of 1.28 GHz. To measure the ADPLL output frequency, it is firstly down-converted to 25 kHz and then sampled with a sampling rate of 5 MHz by an NI USRP-2900 Software-Defined Radio (SDR).

A. Open Loop Tests

Initially, The ADPLL was configured for open loop operation, thereby excluding any loop dynamics from affecting the frequency transient. In this case, the ADPLL output clock only represents the DCO output. Since frequency transients can persist for several milliseconds, multiple SEEs may pile-up. Therefore, the peak frequency error is calculated by subtracting the frequency before the SEE occurs from the peak frequency, as shown in Fig. 7.

The distribution of peak frequency error with three different ions is shown in Fig.8. Among all the peaks, we found out most of the peaks have a positive peak which is aligned with our previous study. [12], [13] However, some negative spikes were also observed with a larger maximum peak frequency error and a smaller decay time as shown in Fig.9. These negative peaks show a larger maximum amplitude with a smaller decay time. Further discussion on the source of these negative peaks will be discussed in section V.

Fig. 8. Distribution of peak frequency error when the ADPLL is configured in a open-loop mode

Fig. 10. Distribution of recovery time for different ions when the ADPLL is configured in a closed-loop mode without employing fast recovery technique

Fig. 9. Some representative examples of positive spikes and negative spikes with Xe

B. Closed Loop Tests without Fast Recovery Technique

Next, the ADPLL was tested in closed-loop mode without fast recovery. Fig.10 presents the distribution of recovery time for different ions. From a control theory perspective, for a given initial frequency or phase error, the loop settling time of a second-order system is primarily determined by the loop bandwidth [25]. The initial frequency or phase error will play a more significant impact if a small loop bandwidth is adopted, which is the case in closed-loop mode without bandwidth switching. Consequently, the maximum recovery time from

negative peaks is significantly longer than that from positive peaks due to a greater initial phase error accumulated during the detection stage. Furthermore, the maximum recovery time from positive peaks is substantially reduced when transitioning from Xe to Ar. However, the maximum recovery time remains approximately the same for Xe and Kr, suggesting that the loop bandwidth is the dominant factor in this case. It is worth noting that the data for Kr in the closed-loop mode without fast recovery might be less accurate. Due to limited beam time, the applied fluence for Kr in closed-loop mode was only 0.6×10^6 ions/cm², whereas for other configurations with Kr, and all configurations with Xe and Ar, the applied fluence was 1.5×10^6 ions/cm².

C. Closed Loop Tests with Fast Recovery Technique

Finally, the fast recovery technique was used to improve the locking process. The ADPLL was configured in closed loop with fast recovery enable for heavy ion tests. The collected recovery time is demonstrated in Fig.11. The maximum recovery time is reduced to $16 \mu\text{s}$ and the highest cross section occurs at $4 \mu\text{s}$, showing a significant reduction compared to the scenarios without fast recovery. However, there are two exceptional cases (not shown in Fig.11), corresponding to a cross section of $1.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2$, whose recovery time exceeding 1 ms. Both of these cases exhibit frequency transients starting with a negative frequency error, suggesting that the prolonged recovery time is attributable to unexpected SEEs

originating from areas other than the inductor. Since these unexpected SEEs can introduce a significantly larger peak frequency error compared to SEEs from the inductor, the designed loop bandwidth may be insufficient to accurately track such large frequency deviations. However, if the bandwidth is appropriately adjusted, the loop will successfully track the frequency error, leading to a substantial reduction in recovery time.

Since a high loop bandwidth was adopted during the fast recovery, the recovery time was dominated by the intrinsic loop dynamics of the fast switching algorithm, instead of being influenced by external perturbations under different LETs. Even though the initial frequency error still has a minor impact on the recovery time during bandwidth switching, the bandwidth level and switching time remain consistent across different ion tests, as it is configured to cover the worst case. This results in an over-configured setting for small frequency errors. Consequently, the recovery time did not show significant differences for different ions.

The maximum integrated phase error with fast recovery is also significantly reduced compared with the injected phase error without fast recovery. One example is shown in Fig.12. The peak phase error is six times smaller with our proposed fast recovery technique. In addition to fast recovery, the detection speed of SEEs also impacts the total introduced phase error. As shown in Fig. 12, when both the reference clock and digital operating clock are doubled, the peak phase error is further decreased. This is because the moving average filter output of the BBPD does not equal zero but deviates slightly due to the limited number of samples used to calculate the average. As a result, the threshold for triggering fast recovery must be set higher than the noise level to avoid accidental triggering. Therefore, when SEEs occur, the filtered BBPD output could be anywhere within the threshold range and it requires several cycles to accumulate errors until it exceeds the threshold, as illustrated previously in Fig. 2. The longer this process takes, the more phase error is introduced into the loop. At higher operating frequencies, however, the BBPD output accumulates errors more quickly, allowing the bandwidth to adjust earlier when SEEs occur. This leads to less phase error being injected into the loop.

V. LASER TEST AND MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Laser tests were conducted to investigate the source of the negative peaks observed during the heavy ion tests and to further verify our proposed fast recovery technique. Fig. 13 illustrates the laser test setup, where the Device Under Test (DUT) was mounted in the PULSCAN PULSYS single-photon irradiation system. For Single-Photon Absorption (SPA) tests, optical pulses were focused through the backside of the wafer onto the front surface of the DUT with a 100× microscope objective, resulting in a spot size of 1 μm.

A. Laser Scan of the DCO Core Area

Since we used the same design flow for the digital part as in our previous work and no sensitivity areas were observed for the digital blocks, our initial assumption was that the source of

Fig. 11. Distribution of recovery time for different ions when the ADPLL is configured in a closed-loop mode with employing fast recovery technique

Fig. 12. Comparison of phase error for Xe under different ADPLL configurations: closed loop without fast recovery, with fast recovery, and with fast recovery and doubled operating frequency

negative peaks originates from the other DCO core area rather than inductor area [16]. A two-dimensional scan over the DCO core area with a step size of 5 μm was conducted to identify the sensitivity area. Meanwhile, the ADPLL output frequency was measured with the aforementioned SDR system. The SPA test results are shown in Fig. 14, which were created by overlaying the measurement results on a photo snapshot of the scan area.

Fig. 14 demonstrates that the switches in the capacitor banks of the DCO exhibit strong sensitivity, resulting in large

Fig. 13. Laser test setup

Fig. 14. Laser scan of DCO core area

negative peaks. The origin of these negative peaks is attributed to SETs in the bottom-pinning biasing scheme used for the PVT and acquisition bank switches. As shown in Fig. 5, for capacitor cells that were not turned on, a SET at the enable node will momentarily turn on M_{SW} and M_{PD} . Consequently, node V_A and V_B are pulled down to ground, connecting the capacitors to the total capacitor bank of the DCO. Besides, A SET on the M_{SW} and M_{PD} can also introduce additional capacitors in the same way. These additional capacitors reduce the DCO output frequency, yielding the negative peaks. In addition to the negative peaks, positive spikes were also observed during laser irradiation in the rest of the area. The mechanism behind these positive peaks is currently under investigation in our group and is beyond the scope of this paper. In this paper, we will primarily focus on the fast recovery technique.

B. Validation of Fast Recovery Technique

Fig. 15 illustrates the frequency transient observed in open loop when focusing the laser onto the center of the inductor with different energy. Consequently, when exposed to a 3 nJ microbeam laser, a maximum peak frequency error of 28 ppm is observed, with a decay time of around 8 μ s. For a lower

Fig. 15. Open loop frequency transient stimulated by microbeam laser with different energies

Fig. 16. Measurement results with and without proposed fast recovery technique under 3 nJ laser irradiation on inductor

laser energy, the peak frequency error is also slightly lower. However, the decay time did not change significantly.

Subsequently, the closed-loop output, without bandwidth switching, is measured to study the response of the loop to perturbations as shown in Fig. 16. The locking of the loop can be defined as when the frequency error falls within the peak-to-peak noise range [26]. The loop takes around 37 μ s to recover from the perturbation. Fig. 17 shows the phase error without fast recovery. Since the phase error is the integration of the frequency error, the longer it takes to recover, the higher the maximum phase error will be.

Fig. 16 shows the closed-loop output with our proposed fast recovery technique. The recovery time in worst case reduces from 37 μ s to 6 μ s. Like in heavy ion test, three bandwidth levels are adopted for fast recovery. Fig. 17 shows the phase integrated from the frequency error. The peak phase error is reduced by around five times with our fast recovery technique. Even after the frequency has settled, a minor phase error still exists. However, this error is negligible, as it is too small to induce any frequency error distinguishable from noise. This residual phase error is attributed to the use of power-of-2 values for switching the proportional and integral gains, chosen for their ease of digital implementation. A more precise

Fig. 17. Phase error integrated from frequency error with and without fast recovery technique

Fig. 18. Measured frequency error when focusing on the switches, with the ADPLL configured in open-loop mode, closed-loop mode without fast recovery, and closed-loop mode with fast recovery.

adjustment of the loop parameters could help eliminate this phase error tail.

Finally, by focusing the microbeam laser on the switches responsible for causing negative frequency errors, the fast recovery was tested, as illustrated in Fig. 18. An additional, larger bandwidth level was introduced to accommodate the exceptionally large frequency error, reducing the recovery time from 1000 μ s to approximately 15 μ s. This demonstrates that our proposed method can still recover from such large negative frequency errors.

C. Comparison

A comparison of this design to other radiation-tolerant PLL and fast locking PLL reported in the literature is shown in Table I. However, the concept of locking time in this paper differs from the locking time in many common scenarios like frequency hopping. Firstly, during frequency hopping, bandwidth switching is activated simultaneously when the frequency needs to switch to another frequency, eliminating

the need for detection, which adds extra time. In this paper, the locking time includes both the detection time and the settling time. Secondly, for frequency hopping, only a static frequency error is present at the initial state. However, the frequency error caused by SEEs varies dramatically, requiring a different strategy for bandwidth switching. Thus, a high loop bandwidth needs to be maintained until the frequency error stabilizes and does not vary dramatically. The definition of the cross section also differs from others. In this paper, we define the cross section as the maximum frequency error exceeds 10 ppm.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF RADIATION TOLERANT PLLS AND FAST LOCKING PLLS

	This Work	[27]	[28]	[29]	[30]
PLL Architecture	ADPLL	CPPLL	ADPLL	ADPLL	DPPLL
Radiation hardened	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Output Frequency [GHz]	2.35-2.83	15-22	0.001-2.5	1-2	3.7-4.1
Reference Frequency [MHz]	40	500	48	50	52
Locking Time [us]	< 16	NA	NA	< 1	5.6
Jitter [ps]	0.335	0.121	0.46	3.09	0.183
Power Dissipation [mW]	14.6	55.7	90	10.8@1.5GHz	5.28
Active Area [mm ²]	0.41	0.17	NA	0.044	0.61
FOM [dB]	-236.8	-240.89	-227.2	NA	-247.5
Cross section	2.67E-5	5.94E-7	6.5E-4	NA	NA
Process [nm]	65	22	NA	65	65

VI. CONCLUSION

Previous work has demonstrated that the proposed ADPLL exhibits good tolerance to TID and high immunity to SEEs, except for SEEs affecting the LC oscillator [16]. To address this issue, a fast recovery technique is introduced, which reduces the recovery time by adjusting the loop's bandwidth. Heavy ion tests have been conducted to validate the efficacy of the fast recovery technique. The measurement results indicate that the recovery time was significantly reduced for ions at three different LETs, although the LETs of the ions had only a minor effect on recovery time. Additionally, increasing the operating frequency of the ADPLL further improved both the maximum injected frequency error and the phase error. In summary, the recovery time and the observed peak frequency error depend on several factors. In most cases, the bandwidth of the loop plays the most critical role. Beyond that, detection speed, including the triggering threshold and the system operating frequency, also has a major impact on the recovery time and peak frequency error. When a high loop bandwidth is adopted, different LETs have a minor impact. However, when a low loop bandwidth is adopted, different LETs have a more significant influence. The decay time of the injected frequency error also plays a role during fast recovery. High bandwidth must be maintained for a sufficiently long time until the next bandwidth level can effectively track the frequency error. Among all the collected data, there are two cases where the fast recovery mechanism failed due to unexpected SEEs originating from parts of the oscillator other than the inductor.

Afterward, SPA tests were conducted to investigate the reason for failures and to further validate our fast recovery technique. Laser scans revealed that the negative spikes stem from SETs in the switches of the DCO capacitor banks. By properly setting the bandwidth, SPA tests demonstrate that our proposed fast recovery technique can still significantly improve the recovery time from these negative spikes. For positive peaks, laser test results show that an SEE with a

maximum frequency shift of 28 ppm was observed under 3 nJ laser irradiation in the center of inductor when the ADPLL was configured in open loop. Without fast recovery, the loop takes approximately 37 μ s to recover from the perturbation. With the proposed fast recovery technique, the recovery time is reduced to 6 μ s, along with a five times reduction in the peak phase error.

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